

DO3 report for Dellinger project

Draft: DO3 report
v0.1, Feb, 2017
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Delivery object 3: Resource exchange structural analysis

Content: National rules and regulations that may affect the exchange of resources will be identified and evaluated, including an analysis of issues that may relate to VAT. This will also include topics related to the resource allocation, accounting and security processes in each country.

Recipient: National providers and NeIC.

Delivery process: Delivery is a document describing the regulatory, legal and national resource management framework that an implementation would have to satisfy along with approaches for operating effectively within the framework. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects will be defined, including staffing.

DO3 components - Feb 2017

Norway:

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Analysis of issues that may relate to VAT.
 - a. Name later in the week
 - b. There have been studies at the university and Sigma2. The external consultants may come up with an incorrect conclusion that invalidates the approach. In NO, a system purchased for research incurs VAT. If a company pays for applied research that is used in a product, the cost of the research is an investment in product development so it subject to VAT. The scientific research is basic research and not related to product development. When Sigma2 buys a system, VAT is paid.
2. Resource allocation (e.g. eligibility to apply for resources)
 - a. Any restrictions in NO? Must be part of academia or a research institute.
 - b. Research institutes - should probably not be contract research, commercial projects should not be part but publicly paid research is okay
 - c. Industry - not for involvement now
 - d. Companies - not for involvement now

- e. Longer term - what would need to be in place? One example would be mechanisms for dealing with data integrity and security. Normal unix security on the systems
- f. If a PI brings in industrial users, e.g. nanotech researchers with a business connection, the non-academic user should be able to get an account.
- 3. Accounting (mechanism for collating usage data)
 - a. Can be provided in any form needed and would be accessible for the project. Are there any privacy concerns? Probably not for a project but possibly for an individual job.
- 4. Security processes (mechanisms for notifying sites of issues/incidents)
 - a. Not sure about the new system but currently have email list for security issues between people. Don't see a privacy concern for the user.
- 5. Operational processes and framework (funding implications for providing resources outside the country, constraints and opportunities)
 - a. Are there any restrictions that the resources should be used inside the country? Don't think so because the national e-infrastructure system is supposed to be responsible and have interactions with the other countries and Europe.
- 6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects, including staffing.
 - a. Need some experience before saying anything about staffing.

Denmark

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Analysis of issues that may relate to VAT.
 - a. Our suggestion is that each NP get approximately the same amount of resources as they themselves provide, i.e., we do not sell anything to each other, and there should not be any VAT issues. In Denmark, the Danish node hours will be bought by DeIC at a low "Danish academic user price" (even if the actual users are from outside Denmark).
 - b. For additional node hours exceeding the node hours bought by DeIC, VAT has to be paid and node hours will be bought at a higher price (when compared to an academic Danish PI).
2. Resource allocation

Any restrictions: For the node hours bought by DeIC as per 1.a, there are no restrictions. For all other projects, both academic, industry, company, and research institutions, a higher price must be paid (as per 1.b), but otherwise it should still be possible to do.
3. Accounting

- a. We use slurm and projects / users can easily extract the node hours used on the system. Each project on our system is granted a specific number of node hours that has to be used within a period of four months. It is not possible to use too many hours.
 - i. If you are over the limit, you can schedule a job with SLURM, but it will not run
4. Security processes
 - a. Normal Linux security.
 - b. Small group, Jens in charge
 - i. Contacting the PI and user through user ID
 - ii. Procedure in place, ie., cutting off the user
5. Operational processes and framework
 - a. No implications as long as it is 1 to 1 exchange
6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects, including staffing.
 - a. Need more experience before saying anything about staffing. We suggest that Nordic users get the same level of support as our local users, i.e., usually enough help to get started / compiling programs etc, but not help to optimise code etc.
 - b. Getting support from other Nordic countries if needed will not be an issue, as long as local admins know what the outside support is doing
 - c. Regular meetings with other Danish HPC staff to be setup if the project grows, but also with other Nordics' HPC staff

Finland

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Analysis of issues that may relate to VAT

One objective could be to avoid VAT to simplify the resource exchange processes. This could be achieved by avoiding any exchange of money or other means as a compensation (consideration) to the hosts. As a rule, taxes are determined by the hosting country and depend on local laws and principles. The VAT analysis has to be done in each participating country.

To some extent there was some research done on the topic for PRACE. The question was whether VAT must be paid from annual member fees, which are paid to the PRACE aisbl. The answer was no, because CSC does not get anything for itself against this payment (like exclusive right to research results). For Dellinger the situation would be

the same: no issues with VAT for CSC because researchers are those who benefit from the resource exchange, not CSC.

2. Resource allocation (e.g. eligibility to apply for resources)

There are restrictions to use Sisu (Cray XC40) by certain nationals defined by US export authorities. At the moment of writing (May 2017) these restrictions apply to nationals of Cuba, Iran, North Korea, and Syria. Other resources are open to all nationals.

The question is about:

- Research institutes
- Industry
- Companies

At the moment, only university and polytechnics researchers from Finland and in certain cases (e.g., PRACE DECI) from abroad can use the resources for public research without paying. The researchers from research institutes must pay for the use, but this might change in the future as the funding for new computing resources will become available. The commercial customers always pay for the use, even when accepted through international collaboration programmes such as DECI. For Dellinger, the same rules as for DECI could be applied.

Some software licences also limit the use for academic use only.

3. Accounting (mechanism for collating usage data)

Mechanisms in place, developed all the time. Accounting is based on the reserved CPU resources, not how much was actually used (i.e., the amount of reserved CPU resources times the actual duration of the job). Memory usage is also charged since the beginning of 2017 (Computing jobs consume either by the number CPU cores or by the number of 4 GB blocks of memory they reserve, depending on which is larger.)

4. Security processes (mechanisms for notifying sites of issues/incidents)

Security incidents would be best to handle locally using CSC's own security processes. Contact persons from other hosts would be important to have for any security issue.

5. Operational processes and framework (funding implications for providing resources outside the country, constraints and opportunities)

As long as it is a resource exchange, no implications are involved. In case of any exchange of funds the Ministry of Education and Culture needs to be consulted, e.g., for allocations above 1 M cpuhours.

6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects, including staffing.

Iceland

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Analysis of issues that may relate to VAT.

Jenný Bára Jensdóttir, Head of Finance Division, University of Iceland

<http://starfsfolk.hi.is/en/simaskra/35028>

Also for the future, most of the resources are expected to come from the University of Iceland.

Has the issue been studied in this context? Checked but no previous work found.

This needs study as it may be an issue in IS if there is any funds exchange needed.

Users of academic Icelandic institutions are not charged for their usage of the IS HPC facilities. Thus if IS users get as much IS provides for others, no VAT issue should arise.

2. Resource allocation

Eligibility to apply: same as NO, academic or research institute, preferably non-commercial applications. Long run: involvement with industry? What are the steps? Not currently a topic of concern - owner of cluster would need to decide. Current cluster - most recent cluster (Mar 2016), academic members from Univ of IS, Univ of Reykjavik and national scientific fund, (Rannis). Not usual for PIs to bring in industry users and should be considered.

3. Accounting

Any privacy concerns about sharing the user data with Dellinger collaboration. This is not currently an issue.

4. Security processes

How to inform others about security - they are the contacts and they have a support email. Response time? 1 business day. Privacy concerns? Can the information on a compromised account be shared? Yes

5. Operational processes and framework

Will there be any implications with the funders?

As long as it is a resource exchange, no implications are involved.

6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects, including staffing.

This is to be talked about more in the face to face. Must see how things work in a test phase to be able to determine this.

Sweden

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Analysis of issues that may relate to VAT.

- a. Name: the Uppsala University lawyers.
- b. Additionally, Sweden agrees with Finland in that the PRACE DECI model should be used as a point of departure for Dellinger regarding a possible model for long term resource sharing.

2. Resource allocation

To be able to apply for and receive allocations on SNIC resources the applicant must be affiliated to a, by the Swedish research Council approved, custodian of funds, which includes academia and research institutes. Furthermore, applicants need to fulfil the requirements in terms of position, i.e. doctoral student, professor et.al. that is required for a specific type of allocation of compute time.

Commercial/industry users in Sweden have their own resources, which may or may not be a part of SNIC resources. SNIC has no control over aforementioned commercial/ industry specific resources.

3. Accounting

SUPR - SNIC User and Project Repository (<https://supr.snic.se/>) has a statistics function for each allocation, which select personnel may make use of.

4. Security processes

An applicant would be required to create an account at SUPR and in the process approve the SUPR user agreement, which defines the rights and obligations of the researcher. SUPR, and the SNIC partner centers has processes in place for dealing with security issues. SNIC also has its own security coordinator and a SNIC security activity with dedicated personnel and a coordinator.

5. Operational processes and framework

SNIC may utilize SNIC resources, via a specific round created in SUPR to participate in the pilot, as the amount of compute rescues offered are limited and due to the exchange mechanism.

SNIC may not utilize large parts of its resources for international researchers due to Swedish Research Council policy.

However, as previously mentioned an applicant would be required to create an account at SUPR - SNIC User and Project Repository (<https://supr.snic.se/>) and in the process approve the SUPR user agreement, which defines the rights and obligations of the researcher.

6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects, including staffing.

n/a